

THE ART OF TRADITIONAL SINGING PERFORMANCE METHODS.

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Annotation: This article discusses traditional singing art, national status and its place in national music, genre features and performance methods in traditional singing art. detailed information is provided.

Keywords: style, work, analysis, status, culture, art, direction, musical genre, performance, music, genre, musicology.

In the performance of the history of Uzbek music art, the art of singing passed from the teacher to the student based on tradition, was formed, developed, adapted to different conditions and has reached us. Folklore sayings in folk art, professional music in the oral tradition - statuses, academic vocals and modern music as an art form that can fully express national characteristics, traditional singing takes the main place. Musicologist S. Bekmatov mentioned in his research that each of the above-mentioned directions has its own style, rules and features in terms of form and performance. [1] Among them, the traditional singing direction, formed on the basis of historical experiences and embodying the most perfect traditions, is of particular importance with its performance style, form, way of performance, complexity of saying, and folkiness. . Since time immemorial, this direction has been bringing out the most beautiful customs, traditions, values and national spirit of the Uzbek people, showing the originality and originality of the rich spirituality of our people in front of the peoples of the world. That is why the tradition of singing and its directions and styles are being formed and developing. The art of traditional singing has become widely popular among the population. They are especially significant in terms of their wide range of singing genres, the breadth of performance styles, and the manifestation of the traditions of the place and space in their unique local styles. Indeed, as a result, performance styles characterized by local elements, and later performance schools, emerged. Andijan, Khorezm, Margilan, Kokand khofiz schools or Ota Jalal Nazirov, Khamrokul Kori, Usta shodi Azizov, Khojikhon Boltaev, Madrakhim Sherozi (Yakubov), Mamadbuva Sattarov, Rasulkori Mamadaliev, Murodjon Akhmedov, Khoji Abdulaziz Abdurasulov, Mamatbuva Sattarov, Jurakhan Sultanov, Mamurjon Uzokov, Komiljon Otaniyozov, Fattahkhan Mamadaliev, Komuna Ismailova, Nazira Akhmedova, Saodat Kabulova, Berta Dovudova, Fakhriddin Umarov, Otajon Khudoyshukurov, Tavakkal Kadirov, Khairulla Lutfullayev, Kamodiddin Rakhimov, Sherali Joraev, Artik Otajonov, Makhmudjon Tojiboev, Munajat Yulchieva and hundreds of other singers have appeared.

Knowledge and practical elements occupy a special place in traditional singing, as in other areas of the art of singing. one such element, and the primary process, is undoubtedly -sound. Everyone has their own tone of voice. We distinguish and separate them from each other based on the color of their voice. The color of the singer's voice depends on the singer's performance skills, word pronunciation, way of saying, melody and tone, and the correlation with the experience of creative skills.

These specific stages, which are at the core of the singing practice, have literally created specific levels, which among the people are singer, laparchi, yallachi, dostan, termachi, ashulachi, interpreter, savthkhan, nasrkhan, He was called by such names as zikir, jahrchi, goyandachi, etymchi, singer and finally hafiz. These were formed in practice as types of singing art. It has

become a tradition to treat each of the performers as “khafiz” who was considered perfect in every way and managed to reach the highest level.[2] For example, hafiz is a term given to a singer who has achieved a comprehensive and high level of performance skills and is an expert in his field. The melodies and, most importantly, the spirit of Uzbek music are reflected especially in hafiz. In the 30s of the 19th century, along with the names of “singer” it has already become an image in our language to call those who have achieved a high level of classical music, i.e., masters of classical music.

If each of the above-mentioned terms finds a full expression of the characteristics of the musical genre, “khafiz” has shown some of its aspects in connection with a number of structural features. “Khafiz” is derived from the Arabic word “khifz”, which actually means “keeper”, “rememberer”. That is probably why, in the past, those who had professions related to performance interpretation and those who embodied aspects of interpretation were considered important in their actions, i.e. memorizing.

By the 30s of the 20th century, it was officially popular to call the performers of large-scale songs belonging to the heritage of classical music and folk songs - skilled singers and famous singers as hafiz. In 1939, the government established an honorary title called “Khalq khafizi”. Famous singers Jorakhan Sultanov, Mamurjon Uzokov and Artikhoja Imamkhojaev were among the first to receive it.

It is known that in the process of historical formation, the peoples on earth have embodied the most beautiful qualities of humanity and have passed down a number of traditions from generation to generation as a legacy. Especially those who paid great attention to the preservation of important events, factors and events in social life, as well as traditions, values, customs and ceremonies related to everyday life. The formation and development of characteristics related to the language, spirituality, and psyche of the people under the influence of social, economic and political events, and the emergence of new trends and directions based on them, was considered one of the main laws of culture. From time immemorial, ceremonies, events and actions related to certain conditions, realities, and spiritual needs have been formed in various forms in various spheres of life. In the process of generations following this or that event over the centuries, the need for them to not be interrupted, to hold the ceremonies when the circumstances require and to continue them regularly has gradually become a picture.

A number of unique performance styles of singing have been created in the musical creativity of the Uzbek people. one of such methods is the sudden singing of a song created in an instant without special training, based on one's own performance capabilities, and it is considered badihagoy among the population. In the science of musicology, badikhagoy means a poem (music or song) created instantly without special preparation, or a musical piece suddenly sung in connection with an event or event.[3] In music, there are examples of genres such as sayings, terma, lapar, based on special badikhaguy, which are characteristic of the art of big songs and bakhshis. In the performance of traditional singers, the song samples are formed in a unique Badikhagoy style. The singer performed the piece in his own way, using all his capabilities.[4] In conclusion, it should be said that the basis of any science is its theoretical part, that is, its theoretical ideas. Valuable information about traditional singing is presented in a number of literatures, such as “The Art of Humility” created by Professor S. Begmatov, “Fergana Singing Traditions” created by Fattokhan Mamadaliev nevertheless, in the art of singing performance,

the issues of “khangs” that occur directly during the performance of the work, why the connecting words are used, the types of their appearance, or in which part they should be used, have hardly been studied.[5]

Almost all makoms, chants, and big chants, which have been passed down orally from master to disciple for many centuries, contain certain tones, connecting words, and vowel combinations. As for the dictionary meaning of khang, it is derived from the word and is found in various parts of ashulla and other professional genres.

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